

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVITY AND ENHANCING IT THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract. Many scholars assert that social media is a potentially useful tool for improving teaching and learning environments. This article highlights how social media can foster creativity and communication and offers suggestions for how educators can incorporate this into their lesson plans. However, the impact of social media on education depends on the integration strategies used.

Keywords: Creativity, Creative thinking. Social media integration, communication.

Annotatsiya. Ko‘pchilik olimlar shunu takidlaydiki, o‘qitishni va ta‘lim muhitini yaxshilash uchun ijtimoiy media bu potentsial foydali vositadir. Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy media ijodkorlik va muloqotni rivojlantirishga qanday yordam berishiga urg‘u beradi va pedagoglar buni dars rejalariga qanday kiritishlari mumkinligi haqida takliflar beriladi. Biroq, ijtimoiy medianing ta‘limga ta‘siri qo‘llaniladigan integratsiya strategiyalariga bog‘liq.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ijodkorlik, ijodiy fikrlash. Ijtimoiy media integratsiyasi, kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация. Исследования показывают, что социальные сети являются потенциально полезным инструментом для улучшения среды преподавания и обучения. В этой статье показано, как социальные сети могут способствовать творчеству и общению, а также предлагаются предложения о том, как преподаватели могут включить это в свои планы уроков. Однако влияние социальных сетей на образование зависит от используемых стратегий интеграции.

Ключевые слова: Креативность, Креативное мышление. Интеграция с социальными сетями, общение.

Introduction

Social media has developed into an effective tool that teachers can use to improve student learning and foster creativity and communication skills of students. Teachers can establish learning communities that bridge the gap between informal and formal aspects by enabling users to share their creations and interact with one another. Social media integration can encourage interaction among students, which boosts creativity and communication. Social media's impact on learning is contingent upon the particular techniques employed to incorporate it into the educational process. Therefore, in order to properly foster student creativity, educators must be deliberate in their selection, creation, and implementation of social media learning experiences. This study looks at how creativity and social media interact to offer recommendations for effective use in learning environments.

Creativity

Creativity is often the ability to find out new and useful ideas. Like intelligence, it can be considered a trait that everyone possesses. It is not just creative “figures” like Leonard da Vinci and Beethoven. It's not just a unique ability to draw a picture or design a product. It is in how we solve problems, how we make decisions. No matter one realizes or not, every person can be creative. Creativity is something that can revitalize objects that are out of notice of detrimental to use. Creative thinking is a key capability that helps individuals and organization deal with and manage change for the better side (Morgan, 2009). This creativity is fundamental to the nature of

the planning process. The society we are living is easily modified via creativity we apply. Creativity allows us to view and solve problems more openly and with innovation. Creativity enables us to open the mind. We can call a society that has lost a creative side as an imprisoned society as the people there closed minded. A creative society is a society which appreciates life of every person as a main value. And all conditions are created for people to manifest their unique creative abilities. There have been so creative contests in the world to change social structure or political construction. The urgency of dealing more effectively with challenges of society cannot be emphasised enough by science (Glăveanu, V. (2015).

Social media

Social media, with its many platforms and apps, has become an indispensable element of modern life and society. Although there isn't a single, widely agreed-upon definition of social media, it can be broadly understood to mean web-based platforms that let people work together, connect, communicate, and create communities through the creation, co-creation, moderation, sharing, and interaction of user-generated content. A number of categories exist for social media, including blogs, wikis, microblogging, idea mapping, social bookmarking, podcasting, social news, collaborative authorship, instant messaging, and social networking sites. These resources are very popular and widely accessible, making them ideal for supporting educational initiatives for students of all ages.

Discussions

As time, people are rapidly and continuously changing, it is crucial that there are people are able to turn problems into opportunities by exploiting creativity and innovation. Often, this demands seeing things from a new perspective and breaking away from traditional ways of thinking that may have lost their meaning. This is like to think out of the box (Glăveanu, 2014). Furthermore, this involves more divergent thinking rather than convergent one. Divergent thinking is an integral process in creativity (Williams, 2004). There are lots of spheres where creativity always haunts. Creativity manifest in different spheres differently even though they have much in common. Artwork can be created in sculpture, paintings, drawing, sketching, performance art, dance, literature including poetry, prose, playwriting, filmmaking and many other spheres. Art is not so easy just as it has only three letters. There is huge message behind this three-letter word. It is much more than just paint and glitter. Art calls for creativity to be truly artwork. Creativity in art also helps minds to develop, not only mentally but emotionally and socially as well. It fosters the ability to analyze and solve problems and make decisions. And all of these activities go beyond the art room. Even if art creators create their masterpieces in an art room or certain place, their spirit stroll away. The creative process is the evolution of spirit, idea, minds into its final form through a progression of thoughts and actions without limit. Because art can't be created in a vacuum condition (Elisondo, 2016). The mental activity of artists begins with impulsion to create and to do. This leads to increased curiosity to see and understand (Glaveanu, 2013). This mental process is similar to those of designers. But they emphasize the need to create and to be original and generate a wonder. They have a unique purposes of change, transfer and modify. Creativity in science is characteristics with the purpose of finding something new in the domain of their own interest. Solving a problem is also an incentive for scientist-artists. Unlike artists and designers scientists are more fixed in terms of place they work and schedule. Creativity in science is more systematic, structured and procedural in comparison to the former two. Creativity in science is based on research questions.

Suggestions

Since creativity plays an important role in human life, educators should be creative in education and use social media effectively. Although teaching with creativity is not officially documented rule, it is unwritten and unspoken code of teaching. Every teacher is supposed to be creative because many researchers claim that Sometimes schools kill creativity. And many scholars agree with this statement for the following reasons. School activities are based on repetition of one and the same actions. Our brains are also lazy and like to follow known patterns instead of reinventing a new process every single time. This tendency makes pupils far less creative and therefore, less efficient in the long run. Another reason is that teachers, directors expect pupils to be very rational and logical. A creative idea cannot be born in an environment limited by logic and rationality. Furthermore, pupils are expected to be exact by having a single right answer to any questions. This is a habit which never motivates pupils to play with alternative ideas, efficiently killing any creative bone in their body. They are highly unlikely to think neither convergently nor divergently in the atmosphere where every question has only one correct answer. One-right-answer theory might work in mathematical problems, but nowhere else it is efficient. Whether it is in sales, marketing or web design, there's never only one correct answer. There exist many different approaches to tackling a challenge and that's what makes a field interesting. All possible answers should be considered and decision should be made based on thorough analysis. Teachers sometimes instill to pupils from young age that they become useless people if they do not learn school loads and chunks of information regarding rules which come across less than twice in the whole life. After these, pupils feel as if they had no relevant knowledge that could help them face a challenge and encounter difficulties. As everything has got exit to go out, this is no exception. Even if pupils never take the time to study the basics properly, they can switch on creativity.

Interestingly, those students who are considered to be school prodigies by their teachers can lose their creativity in the long run. Being too much of an expert seems to be bad condition for creativity to be born as well. If pupils are convinced that they know everything there is to know about their field, they limit their ability to look at problems from different angle. Scientific angle will be their only choice making their brains lie on its sofa, sipping a cup of coffee metaphorically. The brain stops working if it follows only one approach.

Considering above mentioned factors perhaps Albert Einstein once said: "everybody is a genius but if you judge a fish on its ability to climb a tree, it will live its whole life believing that it is stupid. Not only does make fish climb trees but also makes them climb down and make them do a 10-mile run. School, are you proud of the things you have done? Turning millions of people into robots. Do you realize how many children relate to that fish swimming upstream in class believing they are useless? The time has come to accuse the school of killing creativity, individuality and being intellectually abused" (Hasan, 2020). Yet some scholars believe that schools can fuel creativity and innovation as acquired knowledge at schools can be an asset for them to open new knowledge. Karwowski argue that creative abilities are drivers, not brakes of school achievement. Dias and Barroso asserted in their research that creativity depends on to what extend teachers and pupils are putting strain on making classes entail creativity (Dias, 2020). Also, Many scholars asserts that by giving students access to international digital communities and enabling them to design their own personalized learning environments (PLEs), social media has the potential to improve teaching and learning experiences. This can foster a student-centered approach and enhance learning. Because social media affordances—such as association, awareness, editability, identity creation, ownership, persistence, pervasiveness, searchability, self-

presentation, spreadability, and visibility—can help students make connections between their use and educational goals, teachers must empower and support their students to make these decisions. Writing abilities, language learning, technology literacy, problem-based learning, community-based learning, collaborative learning, and self-regulation have all been the subject of research. Social media, by emphasizing the usefulness of digital technology tools, can stimulate student creativity and create a more dynamic and productive classroom environment.

Conclusion

The most important reason to foster creativity is one that is rarely assessed but is key to a child's educational success. If a teacher is creative, students are highly likely to love school and in due course schools become meaningful, satisfying and happy place. Creativity in education also have commonalities with creativity in art, music, science as they all serve similar purposes. As artists use paints and sticks, designers use materials, objects, tools, musicians use musical instruments, teachers also use a full tool kit to apply creativity. They are paper, pen, apps, presentation makers, video makers, blackboard and social media platforms. Social media is considered as most effective tool in educational settings to encourage students' creativity. Teachers can provide students the autonomy to make their own decisions by establishing personal learning environments, . By requiring students to produce results that are visible to outside observers, such as members of the community and content experts, instruction can also foster the development of creativity.

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